

Determination of Xanthates by Reaction with 2,4-Dinitrobenzenesulphenyl Chloride

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ACIDIMETRIC titration in anhydrous acetic acid with perchloric acid¹ using visual or potentiometric indication, may be employed for the determination of potassium xanthates. Some xanthates can be determined by oxidation with potassium iodate² in alkaline medium. Iodometric determination³ of water soluble xanthates suffers from the drawback of requiring great dilution, otherwise the fine suspension of dioxanthogen leads to a false end point due to adsorption of iodine. The titration should be carried out as soon as possible because solutions of xanthates deteriorate leading to erroneous results. The gravimetric methods—determination of a xanthate as sulphate⁴ formed by oxidation with alkaline hydrogen peroxide and determination as silver sulphide⁵ formed by treating a xanthate with ammoniacal silver nitrate—are time consuming.

Xanthates have been found to react with 2,4-dinitrobenzene sulphenyl chloride quantitatively.

Based on this reaction, an accurate though time consuming titrimetric procedure for their determination has been developed. A xanthate is reacted with 2,4-dinitrobenzenesulphenyl chloride in benzene-methanol, the excess of the latter is determined⁶ by titration against sodium methoxide using thymol blue as indicator. The reagent is susceptible

to nucleophilic species⁷. Contamination with such species will lead to high recovery whereas acidic impurities will cause low recovery. Though tested with a selection of xanthates, the procedure seems to be applicable to others as well. Standard deviations recorded in Table 2 reveal the accuracy of the method.

Procedure: A potassium xanthate (25 to 125 mg) prepared and purified according to the published procedures⁸ was dissolved in 5 ml of methanol followed by the addition of 15 ml of benzene. 2,4-Dinitrobenzenesulphenyl chloride⁹ (DSC), in measured excess, was introduced. The mixture was kept for the required period of time,

as mentioned in Table 2 and was titrated against $\approx 0.1N$ sodium methoxide¹⁰, using thymol blue (3 drops, 0.3% solution in methanol) as indicator, to a green colour stable for 30 seconds. Complete details for the determination of one of the xanthates are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF POTASSIUM *n*-PROPYL XANTHATE
Titrant: 0.1283 *M* NaOCH₃; Reaction time—30 min.

Wt. of Xanthate mg	Wt. of DSC added mg	Titre ml	% Recovery
48.4	164.2	3.30	99.50
64.6	208.6	4.05	99.62
88.6	265.0	4.85	99.71
122.6	292.4	4.25	99.57

TABLE 2—RESULTS OF DETERMINATION OF SOME XANTHATES

Xanthate ^a	Weight range mg	Reaction period hr	Average% recovery	Standard deviation ±
Methyl (5)	30-130	1	99.55	0.09
Ethyl (5)	30-90	1	99.80	0.18
<i>n</i> -Propyl (4)	50-120	1	99.60	0.09
<i>iso</i> -Propyl (5)	50-100	1	99.86	0.10
<i>n</i> -Butyl (5)	30-125	1	99.86	0.19
<i>iso</i> -Butyl (6)	30-100	2	99.60	0.20
<i>tert</i> -Butyl (4)	40-120	1½	99.48	0.25
<i>iso</i> -Amyl (7)	25-100	2	99.59	0.33
Benzyl (6)	20-85	2	99.58	0.24
Cyclohexyl (4)	50-120	1½	99.40	0.15

a. Figures in parentheses represent number of determination.

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